

Editorial

Suffering: A Biblical Perspective

Suffering is part of human life and experience, and it has been at the heart of the human quest for meaning. Why this suffering? Why me? Why now? Why does God allow suffering? These are some of the common questions for all of us, especially when suffering falls upon us. Suffering varies from person to person, but the fact remains the same: we all suffer. The Bible gives various nuances of human suffering and shows how we can best endure it.

According to Rev 21:4, it is only in heaven there is no pain, death, or grief. The book of Job shows us there can be two ways to respond to suffering: one that curses God because of suffering and one that praises God, even while suffering (Job 2:9-10). Job didn't question God's sovereignty, but he did agonize over things he couldn't understand (Job 10:2). As St. Paul Says, suffering is not an exception to the righteous as they too will groan under the weight of sin and suffering (Rom 8:20-22). Sometimes we feel that suffering is not without purpose, e.g., Joseph's story in Genesis (Gen 37-50). Joseph's suffering led to many people being rescued (50:20). Suffering is real and mysterious. David felt this struggle when he asked God, "How long will you hide your face from me?" (Ps 13:1). St. Paul Says that all who desire to live godly will be persecuted (2 Tim 3:12; Phil 1:29).

Sufferings are difficult to understand. Sometimes we feel that God uses suffering circumstances to accomplish His will; for example, God uses earthly calamities as agents of change and repentance (Lk 13:4-5). However, the believers know only "in part" many of the mysterious purposes of God (1 Cor 13:9). In suffering God can strengthen us to make wise choices and desire the will of God more than anything else (1 Pet 4:1-2). He may use suffering to help us bear more fruit (Jn 15:2). Suffering produces endurance, character, and hope (Rom 5:3-5; 1 Pet 5:10). According to Heb 12:6, "For those whom the Lord loves He disciplines, and He scourges every son He receives" (Heb 12:6). So, God does it with a loving heart. Eccl 7:14 tells us to take refuge in God even in bad times: "In the day of prosperity be happy, but in the day of adversity consider God has made the one as

well as the other so that man may not discover anything that will be after him.” Indeed, God can use suffering as a means of sanctification (Rom 5:3-5; Jas 1:2-4).

Suffering is not without meaning despite its mystery. It is intended to form a Christ-like character (Rom 8:28-29). Amid impending suffering, Jesus’ example was: “Not my will, but yours be done” (Lk 22:42). According to St. Peter, Jesus left us an example of how to suffer (1 Pet 2:19-21). Jesus says his followers would be blessed when they faithfully endured suffering for His name’s sake (Mt 5:10-12). Jesus, the liberator of humanity, entered fully into suffering and came out victorious (Heb 2:10; 1 Pet 3:18). The ultimate answer to suffering was at the cross when Jesus declared, “It is finished” (Jn 19:30). Prophet Isaiah’s description of the suffering Messiah is very moving: “He was despised and rejected by mankind, a man of suffering, and familiar with pain. Like one from whom people hide their faces he was despised, and we held him in low esteem” (Is 53:3). Paul profoundly desires to share in his Master’s sufferings (Phil 3:10), and he rejoices in suffering for the Christ: “Now I rejoice in what I am suffering for you, and I fill up in my flesh what is still lacking concerning Christ’s afflictions, for the sake of his body, which is the church” (Col 1:24). Jesus says that His people should follow in His footsteps, and that would include suffering (John 15:20). He further states that “whoever does not carry their cross and follow me cannot be my disciple” (Lk 14:27).

Like the prophet Habakkuk, suffering calls us to declare to those around us, “Yet I will rejoice in the Lord; I will take joy in the God of my salvation” (Hab 3:18). Peter invites us to have the same mind: “In all this, you greatly rejoice, though now for a little while you may have had to suffer grief in all kinds of trials. These have come so that the proven genuineness of your faith—of greater worth than gold, which perishes even though refined by fire—may result in praise, glory, and honour when Jesus Christ is revealed” (1 Pet 1:6-7). St. James encourages us similarly: “Consider it pure joy, my brothers and sisters, whenever you face trials of many kinds, because you know that the testing of your faith produces perseverance. Let perseverance finish its work so that you may be mature and complete, not lacking anything” (Jas 1:2-4). Jesus also says to rejoice in persecution and suffering: “Rejoice and be glad, because great is your reward in heaven, for in the same way they persecuted the prophets who were before you” (Mt 5:12).

According to the Acts of the Apostles, “through many tribulations, we must enter the kingdom of God” (Acts 14:22). In 2 Cor 4:8-9 Paul says, “we are afflicted in every way, but not crushed; perplexed, but not driven to despair; persecuted, but not forsaken; struck down, but not destroyed.” We may suffer persecution because

of our faith--especially suffering for righteousness sake (2 Tim. 3:12). Paul says that “suffering produces perseverance; perseverance, proven character; and . . .” (Rom. 5:3-4). St. James underlines this aspect: “Knowing that the testing of your faith produces endurance. And let endurance have its perfect result, that you may be perfect (mature) and complete, lacking in nothing” (Jam. 1:3-4). Peter says that whoever suffers in the body is done with sin: “Therefore, since Christ suffered in his body, arm yourselves also with the same attitude, because whoever suffers in the body is done with sin” (1 Pet 4:1).

Suffering can bring glory to God, for example, the healing of the man blind from birth (John 9:1-3). Jesus says that man’s blindness was to show the works of God through his healing. Lazarus’ sickness was “for the glory of God” (John 11:1-4). When Lazarus died, Jesus says, “Didn’t I tell you that you would see God’s glory if you believe?” (Jn 11:40). Paul’s suffering - his “thorn” in the flesh—tormented him, but he found in weakness the opportunity to boast of Christ’s power (2 Cor 12:7-9). Suffering prepares us for more glory. Paul says that the Christian’s “light and momentary” troubles achieve for them greater joy and eternal glory that outweighs anything they will suffer (2 Cor 4:17-18). The followers of Jesus are asked to suffer for Jesus’ sake to enter into the freedom and glory of Sonship for all eternity (Rom 8:18-30). For, Paul says that “I consider that our present sufferings are not worth comparing with the glory that will be revealed in us.” (Rom 8:18). St. Peter says that when we share Christ’s sufferings, we can rejoice when His glory is revealed: “Dear friends, do not be surprised at the fiery ordeal that has come on you to test you, as though something strange were happening to you. But rejoice since you participate in the sufferings of Christ, so that you may be overjoyed when his glory is revealed” (1 Pet 4:12-13).

Suffering is a testimony to the power and life of Christ (2 Tim 2:8-10; 2 Cor 4:12-13; 1 Pet 3:13-17). This includes the following areas: to glorify God before the angelic world (Job 1-2; 1 Pet 4:16); to manifest the power of God to others (2 Cor 12:9, 10; Jn 9:3); to embody the character of Christ in the midst of suffering as a testimony to win others to Christ (2 Cor 4:8-12; 1 Pet 3:14-17). In times of mistreatment or persecution, believers can seek God, find His blessing, and give a powerful testimony for Christ (Mat 5:10-11; 1 Pet 2:19-20). St. Paul says that he wishes to know Christ by participating in his sufferings: “I want to know Christ—yes, to know the power of his resurrection and participation in his sufferings, becoming like him in his death” (Phil 3:10). The Psalmist says that it is good to be afflicted so that he might learn God’s decrees (Ps 119:71).

Suffering helps us sympathize with and comfort others (2 Cor. 1:3-5). As Paul argues, we are meant to carry each other’s burdens: “Bear one another’s

burdens, and so fulfil the law of Christ” (Gal 6:2). Paul writes in 2 Cor 1:4 that God “comforts us in all our affliction, so that we may be able to comfort those who are in any affliction, with the comfort with which we are comforted by God.” Suffering enables us to keep down our pride (2 Cor 12:7). Suffering helps us to discipline ourselves in righteousness, maturity, and our walk with Him (Heb 12:5f; 1 Pet. 1:6; Jam 1:2-4). In this sense, suffering is designed: as a discipline to bring us back to fellowship through genuine confession (Ps 32:3-5; 119:67); as a pruning tool to bear more fruits (Jn 15:1-7); as a test of our loyalty (Heb 5:8). Suffering brings about continued dependence on the grace and power of God (2 Cor 11:24-32; 12:7-10; Eph 6:10f; Ex 17:8f). In Ps 119:67, 71, the psalmist says that his afflictions were good because they made him more faithful and taught Him God’s commands. Paul says that lessons learned in suffering can equip a believer for future ministry (2 Cor 1:3-4).

Sufferings may become mirrors of reproof to reveal hidden areas of sin and weakness (Ps 16:7; 119:67, 71). Sufferings test our faith and cause us to use the promises and principles of the Word (Ps 119:71, 92; 1 Pet 1:6; Jam. 1:2-4; Ps. 4:1). Sufferings may arise due to our foolish choices: fools suffer harm (Prov 13:20), lazy people become hungry (Prov 19:15), adulterers reap bad consequences (Prov 6:32), etc. We reap what we sow (Gal 6:7-9).

Sometimes we feel that suffering is predetermined and inevitable as St. Paul says: “So that no man may be disturbed by these afflictions; for you yourselves know that we have been destined for this” (1 Thess 3:3). Further, Peter says, “therefore, let those also who suffer according to the will of God entrust their souls to a faithful Creator in doing what is right” (1 Pet 4:19). Occasionally, suffering is considered a consequence of the fall, a consequence of human sin against God (Rom 5:12; 1 Cor 15:21).

Jesus calls blessed to those persecuted because of righteousness: “Blessed are those who are persecuted because of righteousness, for theirs is the kingdom of heaven. Blessed are you when people insult you, persecute you, and falsely say all kinds of evil against you because of me” (Mt 5:10-11). Peter argues that righteous suffering makes us blessed: “But even if you should suffer for what is right, you are blessed. “Do not fear their threats; do not be frightened” (1 Pet 3:14). He further adds: “For it is commendable if someone bears up under the pain of unjust suffering because they are conscious of God. But how is it to your credit if you receive a beating for doing wrong and endure it? But if you suffer for doing good and you endure it, this is commendable before God” (1 Pet 2:19-20). The Psalmist says that “the righteous person may have many troubles, but the Lord delivers him from them all” (Ps 34:19).

In short, according to biblical understanding, suffering makes us think about God, humanity, and creation. It is a means God uses to get our attention and to accomplish His purposes in our lives. Suffering is not in itself virtuous, nor is it a sign of holiness. It is true that we naturally try to avoid suffering at all costs. But suffering comes into our lives for our sanctification and eternal joy. Suffering will come, but God can give us grace and power to overcome every trial.

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